

Sustain2030® SDG simulation game

Developed by: iCONDU GmbH

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Keywords

Climate-change Education, Collaborative Problem-solving, Economics, Simulation-based Learning, Strategic Decision-making, Sustainability, Systems Thinking, Transparency

Figure 1. Image from Sustain2030® SDG simulation game (iCONDU GmbH). Used with permission for educational publication. Rights remain with the creator.

Introduction

The Sustain2030® SDG simulation game (see Figure 1) is based on the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and addresses their interrelationships. Sustain2030 outlines approaches for addressing these goals by presenting the basics of systems thinking.

The target group of the simulation game includes employees in companies and municipalities, as well as employees and students at universities. The idea is to playfully raise awareness of sustainability and motivate participants to take sustainable action.

In the simulation game, players take on the role of a Citizens' Council for sustainable development, representing different perspectives on the SDGs. Their mission is to make a

substantial contribution to achieving the 17 Sustainable Development Goals by selecting suitable measures. A key element of the simulation is the SDG system model, which visualizes the interrelationships among the goals and the indirect effects of decisions. The players face challenges they can only solve together.

Sustain2030 was developed in 2021 by iCONDU, a small consulting company dedicated to driving sustainable transformation.

Facts

Release date:	2021 (first publication: 2019)
Developer:	iCONDU GmbH
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	8–15 (optimum: 8–12) per group
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	3–6 h (depending on the number of players; more time is recommended for larger groups)
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	laptop, projector, internet access, and group areas for each game group
Material:	Role packages with action and role cards, interactive dashboards, and instructional guides
Price:	Semester licenses (including all material as PDFs and a link to the digital dashboard) for educational institutions, and license agreements for organizations and companies (license models on request).

Resonance & Criticism

The Sustain2030 simulation game is used at over 20 universities and in training in various organizations. Many players, like sustainability experts, have expressed strong support for its integration in different contexts.

In June 2022, Sustain2030 won 1st place in the category “Online Platform – Consulting” at the German Award for Sustainability Projects from the German Institute for Service Quality (DISQ).

Sustain2030 is highly effective, but it has its limitations. We have received feedback from lecturers that the simulation would be more robust if the interrelations of the SDGs had been scientifically assessed. Another point raised is that the simulation starts in the year 2021, as it is based on the 2021 German Sustainability Strategy. The feedback will be considered in ongoing adaptations.

Game Principle & Process

As the Citizens' Council, the players face the challenge of achieving the SDGs in Germany by 2030 while keeping all goals equally in mind, as unforeseen events and setbacks may

otherwise occur. The interactive dashboard visualizes the status of each goal and the total performance.

In a total of 20 game rounds, with one round corresponding to a period of half a year, the Citizens' Council gathers to discuss which actions should be taken next. Both the actions chosen and the initial events affect only the system's individual goals. Still, the interrelations of the SDG goal model will then pass these direct changes on to the system in subsequent simulation rounds.

Players work together as a group, taking on different roles with different areas of interest. In each game round, they must agree on which actions to take to use the limited resources as effectively as possible. Their task is to weigh up risks against opportunities and set goal- and resource-oriented priorities. The players represent different interests and therefore must collaborate to develop a strategy. The challenge is to build a shared understanding, make collective decisions, and pursue a common approach. Finding common ground is key to success.

The game has been developed in a way that enables achieving the SDGs and allows many groups to achieve significant improvements. However, the confrontation with the different interests and some coincidental events poses challenges for the players that can be overcome.

The simulation game is based on systems thinking methods and a glass-box simulation that helps players to develop an understanding of the systemic impact of decisions. Dealing with short- and long-term consequences and cause-and-effect mechanisms helps to create a holistic understanding of sustainability.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The game demonstrates potential approaches to addressing the complexity of the SDGs by teaching the basics of systems thinking and improving the ability to shift perspectives and collaborate across disciplines. The focus is on developing an understanding of systems, thinking in complex contexts, and fostering decision-making skills (Zürn et al., 2022, p. 15).

The SDG system model enables visualization of the interrelationships among the SDGs. Furthermore, the interactive glass-box simulation allows users to examine the interrelations and the indirect effects of the decisions made. The long-term effects are documented and displayed in the evaluation area of the interactive dashboard, allowing players to analyze the simulation's course and, by extension, their progress.

The game aims to develop a sustainability mindset by encouraging people to reflect on their own actions and strengthening their perceived self-efficacy, motivation, and ability to act towards a sustainable future. Only if players focus equally on all SDGs and the interrelations can they identify and use leverage points and avoid undesirable side effects (Zürn et al., 2022, p. 16).

After each round of the game, the SDG system model provides students with direct feedback on the effectiveness of their decisions and whether they improved the status of the goals. This helps them to evaluate their decisions and adapt their strategy as the simulation proceeds.

Teachers can be trained as facilitators for Sustain2030. In a six-hour train-the-trainer seminar, teachers experience the simulation game from the player's perspective and gain insights into the scenario and possible debriefing exercises.

Teachers support the simulation game with an introduction to the SDGs and to the game scenario. During the game sessions, they provide support with both technical and thematic questions. Multiple game groups can play autonomously in parallel. For younger students with little prior knowledge of the SDGs, it can be helpful to provide moderators for the game groups to assist in discussions and the handling of the interactive dashboard. Teachers guide the game phase and the debriefing, for example, with reflective questions or additional exercises on the SDGs.

Effectiveness

Zürn et al. (2022) states that the lessons learned particularly mention the complexity of interdependencies and that one should act proactively rather than reactively. This shows that Sustain2030 raises awareness for systems thinking skills. The potential of Sustain2030 is being evaluated in various theses. One thesis investigated the role of Sustain2030 in developing a culture of sustainability, grounded in the Inner Development Goal framework of transformational skills for sustainable development. A further thesis explored the influence of the complexity of simulation games on learning effects on systems thinking skills, using the example of Sustain2030. The evaluation of the surveys shows the importance of awareness of interrelations and understanding for collaboration among players. Another thesis investigated the feasibility of the Sustain2030 simulation game as an integration tool designed to improve the transfer of research into a political context.

The underlying method of Sustain2030 has also been used in different research projects. In one work, the Sustain2030 method was used to implement the SDGs as a basis for a company's CSR reporting (Zürn, 2023).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The Sustain2030 SDG simulation game spans 2021 to 2030, making its timeliness a key factor. In the reflection phase, participants often draw parallels between the simulation and actual political decisions or discussions, which strengthens their long-term thinking skills. The timeliness will be considered in ongoing adaptations.

In higher education, some lecturers indicate that the scientific assessment of the interrelations between the SDGs is a relevant aspect. The underlying model simplifies reality and is based

on assumptions, which are, however, well documented in the model and transparent to the players.

Reviewer(s): Björn Warkalla, Ivelina Dimitrova Karaatanasova

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